

KIOS CoE – Sandboxing use-case 2 (SUC2) Wide Area Protection

1.1 Description

The Synchronized Measurement Technology has brought significant advances to the monitoring and protection of electric power systems. The key element of this technology namely the Phasor Measurement Unit (PMU) can provide synchronized voltage and current phasor measurements in millisecond resolution. The synchronization of the measurements with GPS signal and the high sampling reporting rates have provided the opportunity for the implementation of wide area protection schemes in the transmission power systems. In particular, the presence of two PMUs at the two ends of a transmission line can enable the implementation of a differential protection scheme that is responsible for clearing faults that occurred within the transmission line range. In this context, the SUC2 is related to the investigation of the impact of a Man In the Middle (MITM) attack to a line differential protection scheme. Since this investigation in a real power system will compromise the operation of the system and cause interruptions in the energy supply, a realistic setup was implemented in the KIOS CoE sandboxing.

The general architecture of the setup that was implemented for SUC2 is shown in Figure 1. In particular, from the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system that was implemented in the real-time simulator (OPAL-RT 5707) a transmission line is monitored by two PMUs. These PMUs are a part of

Figure 1 Testbed for Wide Area Protection (WAP)

a larger wide area measurements system that spans in the rest digital twin power system and is responsible for monitoring in real-time the digital twin power system operating conditions. As indicated in Figure 1, the PMU measurements are transferred to the wide area monitoring and control applications through the IEEE C37.118 protocol through TCP or UDP. In the case of the wide area monitoring applications a phasor data concentrator (PDC) time aligns the voltage, current, frequency and rate of change of frequency measurements provided by the PMUs with the same time stamp. In this sense a set of measurements with the same time stamp can be processed from several monitoring applications that usually run centrally to the control centre (i.e., state estimation, monitoring of tie-line loading conditions, etc).

As it was aforementioned, PMUs' measurements can be also utilized in differential protection schemes that aims to clear any faults occurred in the transmission line range. As indicated in Figure 1, the PMU measurements are processed through a differential protection relay installed in one of the two substations (connected via the transmission line) and processes the current phasor measurements from the two ends of the line in order to detect any fault within the line. It should be noted that in the normal operating condition, the currents measurements from the two ends of the line are expected to have less than 1% difference, while in case of a fault in the transmission line the current difference will be more than 20%.

This differential protection relay was designed and implemented in the KIOS CoE sandboxing environment, assuming that transmission line that connects the buses (substations) 7 and 8 is protection by a wide are differential protection scheme. The PMUs that monitor the two ends of the line are communicating directly through UDP with the Typhoon controller in which the logic of a line differential protection scheme was implemented. The wide area protection scheme is integrated through a HIL setup to the digital twin power system therefore in case of a fault detection within the transmission line range, the wide area protection scheme sends digital signals to the breakers of the transmission line to open in order to isolate the fault.

As it is evidenced, a wide area protection scheme is a critical mechanism for the integrity of the whole power system. If the communication between the PMUs and the wide area protection scheme is compromised through a cyber-attack, then the attacker can perform MITM and FDI attacks, altering the current phasor measurements that are received by the differential protection scheme. In such case, the attack can cause the tripping of the line without the occurrence of a fault, affecting the normal operation of the system. On the other hand, the attacker can launch DoS attacks in the communication between the differential protection relay and the PMUs affecting the isolation of a fault in the transmission line and therefore compromising the system stability.

The attack scenarios for this SUC are described in Section 1.2 while the results from the scenarios are discussed in Section 1.3. Information about the datasets that emerged from this SUC are provided in 1.4.

1.2 Attack Scenario (& sub-scenarios)

The attacks investigated in the SUC2 (Wide Area Protection) are summarized in Table 1. Specifically, the attack scenarios deal with MITM attack combined with FDI or DoS attacks that target the fault data injection to the PMU measurements or to the discontinuation of the communication between the PMUs and the wide area protection scheme respectively. In case of the FDI attacks the protocol that is targeted is the IEEE synchrophasor protocol namely IEEE C37.118.

Table 1: Attack Vector for SUC2

Attack Vector	Description
Attacked devices	PMUs
Protocols	IEEE C37.118, UDP protocol
Type of attack	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> MITM with FDI MITM with DoS
Attack vector	Attacker should have access to local/wide area network
Complexity	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> MITM and FDI: High complexity with precise value change of the current measurements in order to deceive the wide area protection scheme for the occurrence of a fault. MITM with DoS: Low complexity by dropping down the connection of the specific communication protocol
Privileges required	The attack is launched either virtually within the digital twin or at the network level without requiring any privileges (e.g., administration rights) to access the device.
User interaction	None - There is no requirement for the attacker to authenticate to launch the attack.

1.3 Analysis of results

This section presents and analyses three selected scenarios (S1-S3) related to SUC2. The first scenario (S1) showcases the expected operation of the wide area protection scheme where a short-circuit fault occurred on the transmission line between buses 7 and 8 of the power system is cleared. In the second scenario (S2), a cyber-attack on the communication channels between the PMUs and the wide area protection scheme (implemented in the Typhoon controller) is considered. Specifically, S2 examines a MITM attack with FDI on phasor measurements from a PMU installed at Bus 7 of the power system. The final scenario (S3) demonstrates SUC2 operation under a MITM with DoS attack. For each cyberattack scenario (S2 and S3), an impact assessment is conducted to show how these attacks can affect the stability and integrity of the system.

1.3.1 SUC2/S1 – Wide area protection operation during a line fault

Figure 2: Normal operation where the protection is able to clear the fault occurred in transmission line between buses 7 and 8 (sinusoidal format).

The first scenario of this SUC emphasizes on a fault in a transmission line of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system. In this scenario, a short-circuit fault occurred within the range of the transmission

line that connects buses 7 and 8 of the power system, significantly increases the current flow of the line, as illustrated in Figure 2.

During the fault free operation of the system (before 10 seconds and after 20 seconds), the line breakers are closed and the transmission line between buses 7 and 8 provides uninterrupted power supply with a current flow of about 274 A. A short-circuit fault occurred at 10 seconds, causes the current flow in the transmission line near bus 7 to spike to 2385 A, as shown in Figure 3.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: Normal operation where the protection is able to clear the fault occurred in transmission line between buses 7 and 8.

As indicated in the Figure 3 (a) and (b), abnormal high currents are experienced in the line 7-8 that essentially impacts the operation of the grid. In order to prevent the spread of the fault in the rest of the system, the current flow through the transmission line is interrupted by the WAP system through the opening of the line breakers when the fault is detected. Once the fault is cleared, the

breakers of the line reclose and the current flow in the line is restored to the nominal value of 274 A.

This scenario indicates that a short-circuit fault on a transmission line can cause a significant increase in the current flow of the line, which if it is not timely cleared can cause instability issues in the system as well as physical damage to the line.

1.3.2 SUC2/S2 – MITM with FDI cyberattack on the PMU measurements used in the WAP scheme

The second scenario of this SUC examines the operation of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system when a MITM and FDI attack is conducted on the measurements of bus 7 which essentially targets the malfunction of the WAP system. This specific FDI attack, virtually implemented within the sandboxing, is highly complex and introduces a multiplicative change to the current measurements before they are received by the Typhoon controller where the WAP system is implemented. As indicated in Figure 4, this MITM attack disrupts the system's operation since the power supplied by the line is interrupted while the attack also causes a system reconfiguration.

Figure 4: MITM and FDI attack multiplicative changes on current measurements of Bus 7 (sinusoidal format).

As demonstrated in S1, during normal operation (before 10 and after 20 seconds), the transmission line between buses 7 and 8 of the system provides uninterrupted power supply, with current flow of 274 A. In this scenario, a MITM FDI cyber-attack is launched, maliciously increasing the PMU current phasor measurements of phase A sent from Bus 7 to the WAP system by 25% (x1.25). The false PMU measurements affect the WAP system of the line since the line breakers are opened although there is not any actual fault in the system. This is because the differential current (difference of the two currents from the two-line ends) is higher than the threshold, thus the WAP is deceived by the attacker. Consequently, the overall operation of the system is impacted, as

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: MITM and FDI attack multiplicative changes on current measurements of bus 7.

demonstrated in Figure 5, where it is evident that the WAP trips the line breaker taking it out of operation due to the MITM FDI attack.

The impact assessment for the second scenario of SUC2 reveals that a MITM and FDI cyber-attack, which maliciously change the current measurements of a bus in the power system, can interrupt the power supplied through line 7-8 and can cause the reconfiguration of the power system. The line trip can overload neighbor lines since they will undertake the power flow of the trip line and might cause their cascading tripping due to their overcurrent protection system. Furthermore, the reconfiguration of the power system affects the network connectivity of the system which is considered as input to several monitoring applications of the power system control center (i.e., state estimation and power flow). Therefore, this malicious reconfiguration affects the accuracy and reliability of the control center monitoring application and consequently the power system operators' situational awareness.

Figure 6: MITM with DoS attack disturbing the C37.118 UDP communication received by the Typhoon controller.

1.3.3 SUC2/S3 - MITM with DOS cyber-attack

The final scenario of SUC2 focuses on a MITM combined with DoS attack which primarily aims to disrupt the WAP system's functionality on the C37.118 UDP communication channel between PMU on bus 7 and bus 8(of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system) and the Typhoon controller. This is executed as an actual attack within the communication network of the sandboxing environment, as detailed in the document describing the KIOS CoE Sandboxing Environment for cyber-physical analysis of EPES. The MITM-DoS attack is illustrated in Figure 6, where the received signals to Typhoon from bus 7 and bus 8, after the attack, remain constant and the same as the last received value normally received.

During normal conditions (before 3.5 s), the transmission line between buses 7 and 8 of the system provides uninterrupted power supply, with current flow of 274 A. When the MITM with DoS attack is launched for 13 seconds (from 3.5 seconds to 16.5 seconds), the Typhoon controller continues to use the previous inputs from the latest current phasor measurements received from the two PMUs.

This is because of a debugging mechanism within the controller that uses the most recently received values as inputs when communication is lost, preventing the controller from going out of service. In this scenario, during the DoS attack a fault in the transmission line occurs as illustrated in Figure 7, which is not cleared by the WAP scheme as it should happen in the case of no DoS attack. This is because the debugging mechanism of the Typhoon controller holds the last value seen before the DoS attack as illustrated in Figure 8. Once the attack is deactivated (at 16.5 s), the C37.118 UDP communication with the WAP system is re-established. In that moment, the fault is detected and is cleared by the WAP scheme as shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8.

Figure 7: Actual fault in the transmission line 7-8 during the DoS attack

The impact of the DoS attack in the power system compromises the reliability of the WAP scheme, while put in danger the power infrastructure since an undetected fault can damage the equipment. Furthermore, the existence of a fault in long time in the system without being cleared will certainly cause instability issues in the system causing brownouts or even blackouts.

Figure 8: Current signals seen in the Typhoon controller (WAP system) before, during and after

1.4 Datasets

Three main scenarios (S1-S3) related to SUC2 operation are demonstrated in Section 1.3. These scenarios showcase the operation of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system and the wide area differential protection scheme under normal operating and faulty operating conditions and under two types of cyber-attacks (FDI and DoS) on the communication channels of IEEE C37.118 protocol. Each scenario is presented with selected time-series plots in Section 1.3, along with a detailed analysis of the processes involved and an impact assessment.

In this section, all the data captured during each scenario's execution have been collected, including electrical and communication measurements. The datasets from each SUC2 scenario are openly available and can be accessed through a Zenodo and linked to this supporting documentation.

Further details regarding the datasets for the three scenarios (S1-S3) of SUC2 are provided in Table 2 - Table 4, respectively.

Table 2: SUC2/S1 datasets

SUC2/S1	Fault occurrence in the transmission line that connects buses 7 and 8
Dataset description	<p>This dataset is related to the operation of the second sandboxing use case (SUC2/S1) described in this document, which examines the operation of a wide area protection scheme in a transmission line which receives data sent from PMUs at the two ends of the lines. Specifically, this dataset corresponds to the first scenario (S1) of SUC2, where a short-circuit fault occurred in the range of the transmission line between buses 7 and 8 of the system. More details about the scenario related to this dataset can be found in Section 1.3.1 of this document.</p> <p>The dataset includes electrical measurements of the current flow in line 7-8 (of the IEEE 9-bus system), in both magnitude and sinusoidal form. The dataset is provided in the form of time-series measurements available as MATLAB (.mat) and CSV files, which were recorded with a 30-second and 40-second time resolution, respectively. The measurements of RMS values were recorded by the Typhoon controller as they were sent by the two PMUs, while the sine wave measurements were recorder through the OPAL-RT.</p>
Dataset purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse the operation of wide area protection scheme during normal conditions and under short-circuit fault. Impact assessment of faults occurred in power systems. Test and evaluate protection scheme to prevent the fault spread in the whole power infrastructure.
Dataset type/format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ELECTRON_SUC2_S1_ShortCircuitFaultInTransmissionLine.mat] [ELECTRON_SUC2_S1_ShortCircuitFaultInTransmissionLineSineWave.mat] [ELECTRON_SUC2_S1_ShortCircuitFaultInTransmissionLine.csv]
File size	32 MB, 15 MB, 547 MB
Data collection	The dataset with the magnitude values was collected through the Typhoon controller which is connected in the loop with the power system digital twin running in the real time simulator. Regarding the sinusoidal format values, the dataset was collected through OPAL-RT which is the real time simulator and run the power system digital twin.
Type of data	Electrical measurements of current flow (in A) from buses 7 and 8 of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system.
Metadata and keywords	Power system, wide area protection scheme, PMU measurements, differential protection, short-circuit fault.

Table 3: SUC2/S2 datasets

SUC2/S2	MITM FDI cyber-attack on PMU measurements of bus 7
Dataset description	<p>This dataset is associated to the operation of the SUC2/S2 described in this document. This use case investigates the operation of a wide area protection scheme which receives data sent from PMUs that their measurements were changed on purpose. More specifically, this dataset corresponds to the second scenario (S2) of SUC2, where a MITM FDI cyber-attack is conducted on the measurements of bus 7, virtually implemented within the sandboxing, and introduces a multiplicative change to the current measurements before they are received by the Typhoon controller via IEEE C37.118 protocol. This supporting document provides more details about the scenario related to this dataset.</p> <p>This dataset includes electrical measurements of the current flow, in magnitude and sinusoidal format, of the transmission line between buses 7 and 8 of the digital twin of the</p>

	IEEE 9-bus system. The dataset is provided in the form of time-series measurements available as MATLAB (.mat) and CSV files which were recorded with a 30-second and 40-second time resolution, respectively. The measurements of magnitude values were recorded by the Typhoon controller, while the data from the sinusoidal waveform were recorder by OPAL-RT.
Dataset purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse the operation of wide area protection scheme during healthy communication and under MITM and FDI attack. Impact assessment of cyber-attacks in WAP applications. Test and evaluate cyber-security solutions to prevent the impact on power infrastructure.
Dataset type/format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ELECTRON_SUC2_S2_MITM_FDI_onPMUmeasurements.mat] [ELECTRON_SUC2_S2_MITM_FDI_onPMUmeasurementsSineWave.mat] [ELECTRON_SUC2_S2_MITM_FDI_onPMUmeasurements.csv]
File size	32 MB, 27 MB, 428 MB
Data collection	The dataset for magnitude values was collected through the Typhoon controller which is connected in the loop with the power system digital twin running in the real time simulator. Regarding the sinusoidal format values, the dataset was collected through OPAL-RT which is the real time simulator and run the power system digital twin.
Type of data	Electrical measurements of current flow (in A) from buses 7 and 8 of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system.
Metadata and keywords	Power system, wide area protection scheme, PMU, differential protection, cyber-attacks, man-in-the-middle, false data injection, electrical measurements.

Table 4: SUC2/S3 datasets

SUC2/S3	MITM with DoS cyber-attack
Dataset description	This dataset corresponds to the operation of the SUC2/S3 described in this document, which examines the operation of a wide area protection scheme which receives data sent from PMUs. More specifically, this dataset corresponds to the third scenario (S3) of SUC2, where a combined MITM with DoS cyber-attack is conducted, as actual attack, in the isolated communication network of the sandboxing environment, disrupting the C37.118 UDP communication exchanged between OPAL-RT 5707, where the digital twin of IEEE 9-bus system was implemented, and Typhoon controller. More details about this scenario associated to this dataset can be found in Section 1.3.3 of D9.3 of this document. This dataset includes electrical measurements of current's flow magnitude of the transmission line between buses 7 and 8 of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system. The dataset was recorded by the Typhoon controller, and it is provided in the form of time-series measurements available as MATLAB (.mat) and CSV files which were recorded with a 30-second and 40-second time resolution, respectively. In addition, the dataset includes network traffic packets captured as .pcapng and .csv files.
Dataset purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyse the operation of wide area protection scheme during healthy communication and under MITM with DoS attack. Impact assessment of cyber-attacks in WAP applications. Test and evaluate cyber-security solutions to prevent the impact on power infrastructure.
Dataset type/format	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [ELECTRON_SUC2_S3_MITMwithDoS_onPMUmeasurements.mat] [ELECTRON_SUC2_S3_MITMwithDoS_onPMUmeasurements.csv] [ELECTRON_SUC2_S3_PMU_C37118_Attack_Traffic.pcapng] [ELECTRON_SUC2_S3_PMU_C37118_Attack_Traffic.csv]
File size	17 MB, 531 MB, 817 KB, 577 KB
Data collection	The dataset for magnitude values was collected through the Typhoon controller which is connected in the loop with the power system digital twin running in the real time simulator. As regards the dataset of the sinusoidal format values, it was collected through OPAL-RT which is the real time simulator and run the power system digital twin. In addition,

	a dataset was collected through the WireShark software, which captures all the network traffic packets related to C37.118 UDP communication.
Type of data	Electrical measurements of current flow (in A) from buses 7 and 8 of the digital twin of the IEEE 9-bus system.
Metadata and keywords	Power system, wide area protection scheme, PMU, differential protection, cyber-attacks, man-in-the-middle, false data injection, electrical measurements.